

Comparative Analysis of Global Food Security Index Components with Population Growth: A Focus on Pakistan and China

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Abstract

Global food insecurity, driven by population growth, is a critical issue. The Global Food Security Index (GFSI) serves as a pivotal tool, evaluating 113 nations on parameters such as affordability, availability, quality and safety, and sustainability and adaptation. This study analyzes GFSI and population growth in China and Pakistan from 2012 to 2022 using statistical tools. Pakistan ranked 84th on the GFSI scale, while China ranked 25th. The population growth rate decreased significantly in China. Both countries experienced increases in GFSI scores, but China consistently outperformed Pakistan. This disparity can be attributed to Pakistan's persistent challenges related to food insecurity. In Pakistan, the analysis reveals a positive and significant correlation between GFSI and the parameters of affordability and availability. However, the correlation with quality and safety was negative and insignificant, while sustainability and adaptation showed a positive but insignificant correlation. In contrast, China exhibited positive and significant correlations across all indicators. When comparing population growth rates, Pakistan demonstrated negative and significant correlations with GFSI and affordability, negative and insignificant correlations with availability, and positive but insignificant correlations with quality and safety, as well as sustainability and adaptation. China, however, showed negative and statistically significant correlations with all indicators except affordability and quality & safety, these are insignificant. This study underscores the importance of tailored policy interventions to bolster food security in both nations, addressing the key factors contributing to their respective challenges.

Keywords

GFSI, Population Growth, GFSI Components, Statistical analysis, Pakistan, China

JEL codes: C12; C13; C18; C44; D78; F68; H12; I18 ; I31; J18; O10; O20; O57; Q18; Q19

Introduction

Global food insecurity is a pressing concern, necessitating sustainable strategies to ensure ample, safe, and nutritious food access (Islam et al. 2021; Shoaib et al. 2021). Food security, as defined by the FAO, involves universal access to sufficient, healthy food to sustain a thriving, healthy, and active life (Islam et al. 2023a; Mc Carthy et al. 2018). It has become a paramount goal within the broader sustainable development agenda (Cole et al. 2018). Organizations such as the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) and the International Food Policy Research Institute (IFPRI) have expressed deep concern and called for strengthened policies to promote food sustainability (Nelson et al. 2010; Shehzad et al. 2023; Timmer 2014). The continuous rise in global population, coupled with increased food consumption, has emerged as a primary cause of the global food shortage epidemic. A key concept of food security is to ensure and enhance food availability (Islam et al. 2023b; Tripathi et al. 2019). The world's annual population growth rate is estimated at 1.2%, with six countries – China, India, Pakistan, Bangladesh, Nigeria, and Indonesia – accounting for half of this growth rate (Carvalho 2006).

In recent years, China-Pakistan's food security has become integral to national security. This aligns with China's efforts to feed its 1.4 billion population. However, both Pakistan and China confront domestic food security pressures, alongside external challenges like Sinophobia in China, trade tensions, global COVID-19 repercussions, and uncertainties in the global food market. Given these hurdles, it is pertinent to assess the practicality of China's current food security strategies. Collaborative efforts between Pakistan and China can pave the way for realistic policies to ensure food security for both nations.

The Global Food Security Index (GFSI) is a comprehensive scale designed by the Economist Intelligence Unit (EIU) and the Barilla Center for Food & Nutrition (BCFN) to assess the state of food security of 113 countries in the national level, drawing from a range of studies (Allee et al. 2021; Singh 2018; Thomas et al. 2017). GFSI Scores are ranged from 0-100, where closes to 100 lead to best score and vice versa. This index is structured around four core dimensions of food security, which encompass affordability, availability, quality & safety and sustainability & adoption (Alhussam et al. 2023; Pyzhikova et al. 2023). It incorporates a combination of indicators, each of which can be considered as factors contributing to food security (Chen et al. 2019; Izraelov and Silber 2019). Utilizing various national-level data sources, the GFSI aims to provide insights into the relative level of food security in a given country when compared to others (Allee et al. 2021).

Literature review

Liu and Zhou (2021) found that China's food security is at risk due to a declining rural population and shifting cultivation patterns. Meng and Fan (2023) reported that since the Eighteenth National Congress of the Communist Party of China, food security has been a top priority, emphasizing basic self-sufficiency in grain and the absolute safety of essential staples. The Two Sessions in 2022 and the Twentieth National Congress reiterated the importance of the "big food concept," which emphasizes adapting to changing food consumption trends and ensuring an ample supply of products to meet the population's de-

mands for a better quality of life. This approach also focuses on stabilizing a diversified food supply to cater to the population's needs. Similarly, Zhang and Lu (2022) and Min and Qinghua (2018) studied China's food security, reporting significant improvements, particularly in availability, access, utilization, and stability. Despite enhanced utilization, imbalances persist, largely attributed to political factors and population growth. In Pakistan, Naz (2022) investigated food security and revealed the country's low ranking in global food security indicators. The study highlighted the necessity of consultations and analyses to address changes in the prevalence of severe undernourishment within Pakistan. Bint-e-Ajaz and Ahmad (2023) examined food security in Pakistan with a focus on affordability, availability, expenditure, and household poverty. Their analysis utilized metrics such as per capita food expenditures and dietary energy consumption. They emphasized the urgent need for comprehensive solutions to improve food security, enhance human well-being, and develop robust food security plans. Several studies have explored food security in both Pakistan and China, primarily focusing on factors such as availability, access, utilization, stability, affordability, expenditure, and crop production. However, this study sets itself apart by exclusively investigating the relationship between population dynamics and global food security in Pakistan and China.

Limitations of the GFSI and Population Growth Rate in This Study

The Global Food Security Index (GFSI) effectively measures the affordability, availability, quality and safety, sustainability, and adaptation of food systems. However, it has notable limitations. The GFSI often overlooks critical environmental factors such as land degradation, water scarcity, biodiversity loss, and climate change, which are essential for long-term food security (Berry et al. 2015; Burgaz et al. 2023; Jansén 2024; Maricic et al. 2016; Naheed and Rukhsana 2024; Odhiambo et al. 2021). Its reliance on economic and infrastructural indicators limits its ability to evaluate agricultural productivity's dependency on environmental conditions, including soil health and climate resilience.

The index also relies on aggregated data, which can obscure significant regional disparities within countries, reducing its utility for addressing localized food security issues. Additionally, it prioritizes quantitative over qualitative measures, underrepresenting critical aspects such as nutritional quality and socio-economic influences on food security.

Despite these limitations, the GFSI remains a valuable tool for assessing food security as it provides a comprehensive framework that evaluates essential dimensions like affordability, availability, quality and safety, and sustainability and adaptation. These dimensions are crucial for understanding a country's immediate food security in terms of economic access and human well-being. Its standardized approach facilitates cross-country comparisons, enabling policymakers to identify areas needing improvement, monitor progress, and allocate resources more effectively (Thomas et al. 2017; Tkalenko et al. 2024).

While the GFSI does not fully incorporate environmental sustainability or account for regional disparities, it serves as a foundational tool for addressing food security challenges. It also encourages discussions on integrating environmental and social dimensions into future assessments. By aggregating data, the GFSI provides a valuable snapshot of global trends, offering insights into how food systems respond to economic and infrastructural changes over time.

Population growth rates also play a crucial role in this study, as they are intricately linked to food security. Rapid population growth can strain food production systems, reduce per capita food availability, and exacerbate challenges such as resource depletion and environmental degradation. Conversely, a declining growth rate, as seen in some countries, may ease pressure on food systems but could also lead to labor shortages in agricultural sectors. Understanding these dynamics is essential for crafting policies that address both population-related and systemic food security challenges.

The population growth rate, while widely used to analyze demographic trends, has notable limitations. It does not account for crucial factors such as the age distribution of the population, a region's capacity to support population increases, resource availability, employment opportunities, infrastructure development, human development indicators, societal well-being, migration patterns, or internal demographic shifts. As a result, focusing solely on population growth rates provides an incomplete understanding of the complex demographic and socio-economic dynamics within a country. Despite these limitations, the population growth rate remains a valuable metric for analyzing demographic trends. It offers a clear and quantifiable snapshot of how a population is changing over time, which can inform critical policy decisions and resource allocation. By highlighting trends in population increase, policymakers can anticipate future needs related to healthcare, education, and infrastructure development. Moreover, understanding population growth helps identify potential challenges, such as urban overcrowding, increased demand for resources, and environmental strain.

This study examines the relationship between the Global Food Security Index (GFSI) and population growth rates, with a focus on understanding how food security components interact with the increasing demand for food driven by population growth in Pakistan and China. As populations grow, the demand for food production intensifies, which can place significant strain on agricultural systems and exacerbate food insecurity. By analyzing the GFSI in conjunction with population growth trends, the study seeks to identify areas where food supply may fail to meet demand, expose vulnerabilities within food systems, and provide actionable insights for policymaking. This comparative analysis is critical for devising sustainable strategies to ensure that future populations have reliable access to sufficient and nutritious food.

Problem statement and objective of the study

Despite significant global attention to food security and the establishment of frameworks like the Global Food Security Index (GFSI), there remains a gap in comprehensive studies examining the individual components of the GFSI and their relationship with population growth rates, particularly in the contexts of countries like Pakistan and China. While the GFSI addresses critical dimensions such as affordability, availability, quality, safety, sustainability, and adaptation of food systems, there is a notable lack of comparative analysis on how these components interact with population growth. To date, this specific investigation has not been undertaken.

This study seeks to bridge this gap by offering valuable insights into the dynamics between GFSI components – including affordability, availability, quality and safety, and sustainability and adaptation – and population growth rates, with a particular emphasis on Pakistan and China.

Materials and methods

Data Collection

The Global Food Security Index (GFSI), developed through a collaboration between the Economist Intelligence Unit (EIU) and the Barilla Center for Food & Nutrition (BCFN), serves as a comprehensive framework for assessing and ranking global food security. The GFSI evaluates food security through four key dimensions: affordability, availability, quality & safety, and sustainability & adaptation. This study utilizes GFSI data spanning 2012 to 2022, analyzing these dimensions in detail. Additionally, it incorporates data on annual population changes from 2012 to 2022, sourced from the United Nations World Population Prospects, with a specific focus on Pakistan and China.

Reliability analysis

Reliability analysis is a statistical method used to assess the consistency and stability of measurements or scores obtained from a particular test or set of items (Hajjar 2018; Kimberlin and Winterstein 2008). It helps researchers determine the extent to which the results from a measurement procedure are dependable and can be trusted. Cronbach's Alpha is a widely used statistic to measure the internal consistency or reliability of a test or scale (Islam and Shehzad 2022; Vaske et al. 2017). The value of Cronbach's Alpha ranges from 0 to 1, with higher values indicating greater internal consistency and lower values suggesting weaker reliability.

$$\alpha = \frac{m}{m-1} \left(1 - \frac{\sum \delta_i^2}{\delta_T^2} \right),$$

where

m = number of items,

δ_i^2 = i th item variance;

δ_T^2 = aggregates items variance.

Comparative analysis using correlation

The GFSI index and its components from 2012 to 2022 are used to compare their significance and basic statistics. Graphical presentations are employed to illustrate these basic statistics. Correlation coefficients are calculated to assess the significance of the components in relation to the overall GFSI score and population growth.

$$r = \frac{\sum (x - \bar{x})(y - \bar{y})}{\sqrt{\sum (x - \bar{x})^2 * \sum (y - \bar{y})^2}},$$

where

\bar{x} = mean of variables "x",

\bar{y} = mean of variables "y".

Hypothesis testing

The hypothesis explores the correlation between the Global Food Security Index (GFSI) and population growth with respect to the components of the GFSI. The null hypothesis (H_0) posits that there is no significant correlation between GFSI and population growth

concerning its components, while the alternative hypothesis (H_1) suggests that there is a significant correlation between these variables. This hypothesis aims to examine whether changes in population growth are meaningfully related to the components of the GFSI, a critical aspect of understanding the dynamics of global food security. The hypotheses are formulated as follows:

H_0 : Correlation found in-significant for GFSI & Population growth against GFSI components.

H_1 : Correlation found significant for GFSI & Population growth against GFSI components.

Results and discussions

Reliability analysis

Table 1 presents the results of the reliability analysis using Cronbach's Alpha coefficients for Pakistan and China. For Pakistan, the Cronbach's Alpha coefficient is 0.60, indicating a moderate degree of internal consistency reliability. In contrast, China has a Cronbach's Alpha coefficient of 0.85, reflecting a high level of internal consistency reliability.

Analysis using correlation coefficients

Table 2 presents a comparative analysis of the GFSI, its components, and the population growth rate for Pakistan and China. The GFSI rank for Pakistan stood at 84th in 2022, compared to 94th in 2012. In contrast, China's GFSI rank improved from 49th in 2012 to 25th in 2022.

Similarly, the population growth rate (PGR) for Pakistan decreased from 2.14% in 2012 to 1.74% in 2022, a reduction of approximately 18.7%. For China, the PGR decreased from 0.67% in 2012 to 0.22% in 2022, marking a decrease of 67%. These statistics indicate that China has been more successful in controlling its population growth.

Pakistan's GFSI score increased from 43.5 in 2012 to 52.2 in 2022, a rise of 20%, while China's GFSI score grew from 60.5 in 2012 to 74.2 in 2022, showing a 22.6% increase. The component scores for affordability, availability, and sustainability & adaptation increased by 26.1%, 48.7%, and 10.2% in Pakistan, respectively, while China's scores for these components increased by 32.9%, 22.8%, and 19.0%. The quality and safety score decreased by 5.5% for Pakistan, but increased by 11.1% for China.

The negative change in quality and safety for Pakistan and the positive improvement in China's score reflect differing trends in food security between the two countries. The components of affordability, availability, and sustainability & adaptation had a positive impact on GFSI scores in both countries. Overall, China's GFSI and its components showed better performance compared to Pakistan, largely due to the more favorable trends in population growth and the quality and safety score.

Table 1. Cronbach's Alpha for Pakistan and China

Cronbach's Alpha	Pakistan	China
Coefficients	0.60	0.85

Source: authors' calculations

Table 2. Comparative analysis of GFSI, GFSI components and population growth rate

Countries	Years	GFSI Rank	GFSI Score	Affordability Score	Availability Score	Quality & Safety Score	Sustainability & Adaptation Score	Population Growth Rate (%)
Pakistan	2012	94	43.5	47.5	39.2	52.3	34.2	2.14
	2022	84	52.2	59.9	58.3	49.4	37.7	1.74
	Change (%)	--	20.0	26.1	48.7	-5.5	10.2	-18.7
China	2012	49	60.5	65	64.5	64.8	45.8	0.67
	2022	25	74.2	86.4	79.2	72	54.5	0.22
	Change (%)	--	22.6	32.9	22.8	11.1	19.0	-67.2

Source: authors' calculations

Figure 1. Comparative analysis of GFSI, GFSI components and population growth rate. Source: authors' calculations

Table 3 presents the relationships and significance of the GFSI components and population growth in relation to GFSI components. For Pakistan, when comparing with the GFSI score, positive relationships are observed for affordability, availability, and sustainability and adaptation, with coefficients of 0.852, 0.880, and 0.251, respectively. However, a negative relationship is found for quality & safety, with a coefficient of -0.437.

For China, all GFSI components show positive relationships with the GFSI score. The results indicate that the correlation is statistically significant for affordability and availability, but insignificant for quality and safety and sustainability and adaptation for Pakistan. In contrast, all the correlation coefficients for GFSI components are statistically significant for China.

When comparing population growth rate with the GFSI and its components, a negative relationship is found for the GFSI score, affordability, and availability in Pakistan, with coefficients of -0.742, -0.802, and -0.514, respectively. However, positive relationships are observed for quality and safety and sustainability and adaptation, with coefficients of 0.372 and 0.133, respectively.

For China, negative relationships are found for the GFSI score, affordability, availability, quality and safety, and sustainability and adaptation, with coefficients of -0.661, -0.511, -0.651, and -0.534, respectively.

In terms of the significance of correlation coefficients, for Pakistan, significant relationships are found between population growth rate and the GFSI score as well as affordability, but other correlations are insignificant. For China, all the indicators show positive and significant relationships with GFSI. When comparing population growth rate with different indicators in China, significant negative relationships are observed for GFSI, availability, and sustainability and adaptation, while the relationships with affordability and quality and safety are negative and insignificant.

Table 3. Correlations and significance of GFSI & Population growth against GFI components

Parameters	GFSI	Affordability	Availability	Quality & Safety	Sustainability & Adaptation
GFSI Pakistan	--	0.852** (0.001)	0.880** (0.00)	-0.437 (0.178)	0.251 (0.456)
GFSI China	--	0.949** (0.00)	0.804** (0.003)	0.833** (0.001)	0.906** (0.00)
Population Growth Rate (Pakistan)	-0.742** (0.009)	-0.802** (0.003)	-0.514 (0.106)	0.372 (0.26)	0.133 (0.697)
Population Growth Rate (China)	-0.661* (0.027)	-0.511 (0.108)	-0.651* (0.03)	-0.534 (0.091)	-0.751** (0.008)

Source: authors' calculations. Note: Values in parenthesis show the significance (**statistically significant)

This research reaffirms the findings of Guo et al. (2021), Liu and Zhou (2021), Zhang and Lu (2022), and Min and Qinghua (2018) regarding the enhanced status of China's food security, particularly highlighting improvements in availability, access, utilization, and stability. The study further underscores that, despite these improvements, imbalances persist in sustainability and adaptation, with population growth negatively impacting food security in China.

For Pakistan, the findings confirm the results of Naz (2022), Bint-e-Ajaz and Ahmad (2023), and Islam et al. (2023a), which indicate that Pakistan ranks lower in food security. Additionally, this study highlights that population growth is adversely affecting the GFSI, particularly in affordability and availability, while having a slightly positive effect on quality and safety and sustainability and adaptation in Pakistan.

Policy implications

Policy implications for China

China's significant reduction in population growth rate highlights the effectiveness of population control policies, such as the one-child policy. Continued efforts in this direction could further ease the pressure on food security by focusing on improvements in quality, safety, sustainability, and adaptation. Overall, China performs better in food security compared to Pakistan. However, it is crucial to address the adverse effects of population growth on the GFSI and its components to ensure long-term food security. By implementing strategies that enhance food quality and sustainability, along with continued management of population growth, China can secure long-term food security and mitigate future pressures on its food system.

Policy implications for Pakistan

Pakistan's food security is closely tied to its population growth. To alleviate the pressure on food resources, the government should prioritize implementing effective population management strategies, such as family planning programs and contraception education, alongside ongoing efforts to strengthen all components of the GFSI. This integrated approach can help ease the burden on food supply and improve overall food security. Food quality and safety are negatively impacted, as reflected in their relationship with the GFSI, indicating that this issue is critically affecting Pakistan and undermining the country's food security efforts. It is essential to develop and implement policies focused on improving food quality and safety in Pakistan.

Given that population growth is negatively correlated with the GFSI, addressing issues related to affordability, quality, and safety is crucial to ensuring food security. Policies aimed at reducing population growth and improving the GFSI score will be essential for securing a food-secure future. By addressing these challenges, Pakistan can establish a stronger foundation for achieving sustainable food security.

Conclusions

Global food insecurity is a critical issue driven by population growth, and ensuring access to safe, ample, and nutritious food is essential for the world. The global population growth rate is expected to rise significantly, with China, India, Pakistan, Bangladesh, Indonesia, and Nigeria leading this increase. Food security in China and Pakistan is closely linked to national security.

The Global Food Security Index (GFSI) evaluates countries based on four key components: affordability, availability, quality and safety, and sustainability and adaptation. This research analyzes the relationship between the GFSI and population growth for Pakistan and China, using data from 2012 to 2022. Correlation coefficients are applied to assess the significance of population growth on the overall GFSI score and its components.

Pakistan ranks lower on the Global Food Security Index compared to China. While Pakistan's population growth rate has declined moderately, China has seen a more substantial decrease, reflecting effective population control measures. This difference can be attributed to Pakistan's ongoing challenges with population growth and its lower scores in quality and safety.

In Pakistan, the GFSI showed a positive and significant relationship with affordability and availability, but a negative, insignificant relationship with quality and safety. The relationship with sustainability and adaptation was positive but insignificant. In contrast, China exhibited positive and significant relationships between the GFSI and all components.

Regarding population growth, Pakistan exhibited a negative and significant relationship with GFSI and affordability, a negative but insignificant relationship with availability, and positive but insignificant correlations with quality and safety and sustainability and adaptation. In contrast, China displayed negative and statistically significant correlations with all indicators except affordability and quality and safety, where the correlations were negative but insignificant.

This study provides valuable policy recommendations to enhance food security in both countries by addressing key contributing factors. Further research can expand this analysis to include more countries and additional subcomponents of the GFSI. The limitations of the GFSI can be explored using alternative tools, and regression analysis could be employed to examine cause-and-effect relationships and assess the influence of one indicator on another. Additionally, comparative cross-sectional and time series analyses, utilizing statistical and machine learning methods, can offer deeper insights.

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Author's contributions

Muhammad Islam: Contributed to drafting, introduction, discussions, conducting data analysis, providing descriptions, formulating conclusions, developing methodologies, and outlining policy implications.

Ghareeb A. Marei: Contributed with revisions, drafting, analysis, descriptions, discussions, and formulating policy implications.

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Conflict of interest

All authors declared no conflict of interest.

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